

ParticleTransformer is all you need for reconstructing hadronic tau leptons

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Abstract

The large number of $Z \rightarrow \tau\tau$ events expected during the TeraZ program at FCC-ee will allow for precision measurements and searches for physics beyond the Standard Model, requiring accurate reconstruction of hadronically decaying tau leptons. This reconstruction is particularly challenging due to the presence of undetected neutrinos and the diverse topology of hadronic tau decays, making the design of robust heuristic reconstruction algorithms challenging. In this work, we present the first fully machine learned hadronic tau reconstruction approach tuned for FCC-ee studies. The reconstruction is formulated as a set of complementary tasks, including tau identification, decay mode classification, charge reconstruction, and full four-momentum regression. The algorithms are evaluated on fully simulated electron-positron collision samples with realistic detector effects using the CLD detector setup. We compare dedicated task-specific models with a unified multi-task model and quantify their performance in a granular manner across all reconstruction tasks. Both approaches achieve per-mille-level tau mis-identification rates at high signal efficiency, decay mode classification F1 scores of up to 0.95 for the dominant channels, and sub-per-mille charge mis-identification rates, outperforming a conventional jet-charge estimator by up to two orders of magnitude. For the full kinematic reconstruction, the models achieve per-mille-level angular resolution and percent-level visible transverse momentum resolution, exceeding the performance of reconstruction-level jet observables. While the dedicated training approach achieves the best kinematic reconstruction performance, the unified multi-task approach attains slightly better performance for the classification tasks while using only about one-quarter of the trainable parameters. The resulting models provide a realistic high-performance solution for hadronic tau reconstruction at FCC-ee, offering identification, charge discrimination, decay mode analysis and full kinematic reconstruction.

1 Introduction

During TeraZ, the first operational stage of the envisioned Future Circular Collider (FCC) experiment, approximately $\mathcal{O}(10^{11})$ $Z \rightarrow \tau\tau$ events are expected to be produced. Making full use of this dataset for precision measurements [1] and other analyses involving hadronically decaying tau leptons requires accurate τ_h reconstruction.

However, reconstructing the τ lepton is inherently challenging. Due to its very short lifetime of only 290 fs, corresponding to an average decay length of $c\tau = 87 \mu\text{m}$, the τ cannot be observed directly and must be inferred from its decay products. These products always include at least one ν_τ that escapes detection, reducing the reconstructable final state. Approximately 1/3 of τ decays proceed leptonically and 2/3 hadronically. Since leptonic decays are naturally accounted for by electron and muon reconstruction, this work focuses exclusively on hadronically decaying τ leptons, denoted as τ_h .

The experimentally accessible decay products define the visible four-momentum of the τ_h candidate. Accurately reconstructing the full visible four-momentum (p^μ) of the τ_h candidate, specifically its transverse momentum, invariant mass, and angular direction, is a fundamental prerequisite for a wide range of precision measurements at future colliders. The reconstruction of the visible transverse momentum (p_T^{vis}) and mass (m^{vis}) is critical for determining the true invariant mass of heavy resonances, such as the Higgs and Z bosons, decaying into tau pairs. Because the ν_τ escapes detection, the visible decay products represent only a fraction of the parent particle's kinematics, resulting in a visible mass distribution that is significantly shifted and broadened [2, 3]. Robust visible kinematic regression is therefore the necessary first step for any downstream algorithm aiming to estimate the missing neutrino momenta and recover the true resonance mass [4]. Furthermore, precise angular reconstruction (pseudorapidity η and azimuthal angle ϕ) is essential for both mass approximation algorithms and polarization studies [1]. Due to the tau lepton's short lifetime, its spin and parity must be inferred from the angular and energy distributions of its visible decay products. In the context of $H \rightarrow \tau\tau$ decays, measuring the angle between the decay planes of the two tau leptons provides sensitivity to the CP structure of the Higgs Yukawa coupling [5]. Finally, many standard mass reconstruction techniques utilize the collinear approximation for highly boosted topologies, which assumes the undetected neutrino is emitted in the same direction as the visible hadronic products; thus, exceptional resolution of the τ_h direction is necessary [5, 6].

Beyond kinematic regression, accurate reconstruction of the hadronic tau charge (q) is required for both Standard Model measurements and searches for new physics. In di-tau resonance searches (such as $Z \rightarrow \tau\tau$ and $H \rightarrow \tau\tau$), the primary method for reducing combinatorial background is the Opposite-Sign (OS) requirement. Since heavy neutral resonances decay into a τ^+ and a τ^- , selecting candidate pairs with opposite charges suppresses backgrounds from W +jets and QCD multijet processes, where misidentified jets have uncorrelated charges [7]. Misidentifying the τ_h charge causes true signal events to fail this selection, reducing the statistical power of the analysis. Charge reconstruction is also central to the physics program of the FCC. At the Tera- Z phase, extracting the electroweak mixing angle ($\sin^2 \theta_W^{\text{eff}}$) relies on measuring the forward-backward asymmetry (A_{FB}) and polarization of tau leptons in Z -boson decays [8]. Furthermore, searches for charged Lepton Flavor Violation (cLFV), such as $Z \rightarrow \mu^\pm \tau^\mp$, depend on charge identification to ensure charge conservation and classify the event topology [9].

In general, τ_h reconstruction algorithms approach the problem from one of two directions: directly predicting high-level τ_h quantities (such as Tau ID, decay mode, charge, and four-momentum) from the decay constituents in an end-to-end fashion, or fully reconstructing the individual decay products, leaving the inference of the properties of the τ_h from the decay products to a subsequent model. Classical algorithms, such as the hadron-plus-strips (HPS) [7, 10] at CMS, follow the latter approach, combining charged tracks and calorimeter strips into decay mode specific τ_h candidates and applying isolation and quality cuts for candidate selection. In this paper, we aim to provide the first comprehensive end-to-end model to reconstruct the full τ_h object for future colliders. This approach is intended for analyses that require high-level reconstructed objects for event selection. A full constituent-level reconstruction is required for analyses sensitive to the internal structure of the τ_h decay, such as $H \rightarrow \tau\tau$ [11] and τ polarization studies [1], and is not addressed in this paper.

At present, the state of the art τ_h reconstruction algorithms are based on deep learning and provide important context for this work. At CMS, the DeepTau algorithm [12] has established a strong benchmark for τ_h identification using a deep neural network with convolutional layers, and more recently alternative approaches based on graph neural networks and ParticleTransformer architectures have been

explored [13]. A notable development in this direction is the Tau Transformer (TaT), which utilizes an embedding module and self-attention layers to process the multimodality of the input representation, demonstrating significantly improved background rejection over DeepTau [5]. A systematic comparison of DeepTau, ParticleNet [14], and UParT [15] has also been carried out [16]. Specialized variants targeting particular physics regimes have furthermore been developed, including DisTau [17] for τ_h candidates displaced from the primary vertex, Boosted DeepTau [18] for highly boosted topologies where the two τ leptons overlap, and TauNet [19], a dedicated energy-flow neural network targeting low- p_T τ_h reconstruction in the CMS Run 3 scouting data stream. At ATLAS, the τ_h reconstruction and identification employs recurrent neural networks (RNNs) for both the identification and electron rejection tasks, as described in Ref. [20]. In lepton collider environments, the TauFinder algorithm [21, 22], originally developed for linear colliders [21] and more recently applied to muon collider studies, is a notable example of a τ_h reconstruction approach optimized for such conditions. It targets decay modes with one or three charged tracks and applies sequential quality cuts on the reconstructed candidates. While these algorithms mostly address individual reconstruction tasks, the present work aims to provide a unified, transformer-based approach that can be directly deployed for ongoing and upcoming FCC sensitivity analyses.

It has been shown previously that the ParticleTransformer [23] based high-level reconstruction algorithm performs well on the following tasks: τ_h identification [24], decay mode and p_T regression [25]. In this work we expand the range of reconstruction tasks to include full 4-momentum regression, tau identification, charge identification and decay mode classification in a single, unified model. In principle, this approach is extensible to additional properties such as the decay vertex [26], needed for studying displaced vertex signatures for example in analyses featuring long-lived particles (LLPs) [27–29] such as heavy neutral leptons (HNLs) [30, 31].

We study two approaches, training a dedicated model separately for each of the four tasks, referred to as SingleParTau, and training a unified multi-task model, referred to as MultiParTau, on all four tasks simultaneously. The performance of both approaches is evaluated in a granular way, using task-specific metrics for each of the four reconstruction tasks.

An overview of the dataset and its features is given in Sec. 2, followed by the introduction to the architecture and training strategies of two models. The results are presented in Sec. 4 and a short summary and thoughts about the next steps are given in Sec. 5.

2 Dataset

With this paper we introduce the new version of the jet-based Fu τ ure dataset for τ_h reconstruction [32]. This dataset is aimed to align with the current efforts of the envisioned FCC [33, 34] experiment. We used the CLIC Like Detector (CLD) detector concept [35], one of the possible detectors at FCC, for event generation, simulation and reconstruction.

Furthermore, the dataset is updated to include approximately two million e^+e^- collision events with $Z/\gamma^* \rightarrow \tau\tau$ (signal) and $Z/\gamma^* \rightarrow qq$ (background) samples generated at $\sqrt{s} = 91$ GeV, corresponding to the TeraZ run.

The Monte Carlo generation and event reconstruction are described in Sec. 2.1 and the input features for the models in Sec. 2.2. This public dataset can be found in Ref. [32] and the software used to produce it in Ref. [36].

2.1 Monte Carlo samples and event reconstruction

The e^+e^- collision events in this dataset are generated using PYTHIA8 [37] with default tunes configured via the Key4HEP generation wrapper. The generation assumes a clean environment without beam-induced backgrounds; beamstrahlung and beam energy spread effects are not enabled, since their impact

on τ_h reconstruction and identification is expected to be negligible. The decays of the τ leptons are handled directly by the default PYTHIA8 decay tables, without the use of external polarization packages.

The subsequent full detector simulation is performed with Geant4 [38] using the FTFP_BERT physics list. The detector geometry utilizes the CLD_o2_v07 setup, an evolution of the CLD detector concept envisaged for the Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee) [35]. The CLD features an all-silicon vertex and tracking system, highly granular calorimeters (a silicon-tungsten ECAL and a scintillator-steel HCAL), and a superconducting solenoid providing a 2 T magnetic field.

The simulated events are reconstructed using the Marlin [39] and Key4HEP [40] software stack (release 2025-05-29). Event reconstruction is performed in a clean environment without background overlay. Charged particle tracks are reconstructed using the ConformalTracking algorithm [41] with optimized settings for the CLD_o2_v07 geometry, and prepared in the EDM4HEP [42] format. The features used by the τ_h identification and reconstruction model(s) are extracted from the particle flow candidates reconstructed by PandoraPF [43, 44].

All generator cards, steering configurations, and PandoraPF calibration constants are managed via the dedicated CLD configuration repository [45].

2.2 Input features and validation

The dataset is based on jets clustered from particle flow candidates reconstructed by PandoraPF. Jets are clustered using `ee_genkt` [46] algorithm with $p = -1$, $R = 0.4$ and with no minimum p_T cut applied. The cut on p_T is removed in this version in order to retain jets matched to τ_h candidates with p_T of a few GeV, relevant for the TeraZ physics program.

Each charged particle flow candidates will be assigned with a set of track parameters d_{xy} , d_z , S_{d_z} and $S_{d_{xy}}$ calculated using the track parametrization from Ref. [47]. The corresponding value for neutral particle flow candidates are set to dummy values to maintain a consistent feature set. The complete list of features used in the training are listed in the Table 1.

In order to associate the reconstruction level jets used as an input the models with the generator-level truth, the generator-level τ_h^{vis} is matched to both generator-level jets and reconstructed jets within a cone of size $\Delta R < 0.4$. A total of four target values will be associated to each reconstruction-level jet:

- Binary label `isTau`. Set to `True` if matched to generator-level τ_h
- Categorical target with 6 classes corresponding to the decay modes targeted in this study
- Binary classification label with boolean encoding 0, 1 corresponding to the generator-level τ_h charges -1, +1
- Multi-value regression target p^μ corresponding to the generator-level visible τ_h four-momentum.

In order to balance the τ_h identification task across jet kinematics, each reconstructed jet is assigned a classification weight w_{cls} according to the signal and background contribution to the given bin in the polar angle-momentum (θ - p) space. Weights w_i for each bin i are calculated according to Eq. 1:

$$w_i = \frac{\min(N_i^{sig}, N_i^{bkg})}{N_i^{sig}} \quad (1)$$

A total of 5.33 M (0.59 M) signal $Z/\gamma^* \rightarrow \tau\tau$ and 35.36 M (3.93 M) background $Z \rightarrow qq$ jets are used for training (testing). The training dataset is further divided into train-validation subsets, allocating 20% of the jets for validation, with the rest of them being used for training. This constitutes a total of 72-18-10% split of the full generated dataset for training-validation-testing.

Table 1: Jet constituent (particle flow candidate)-level input features used in the model.

Constituent kinematics		
Category	Feature	Description
Kinematics (absolute)	p_x	Candidate momentum x-component
	p_y	Candidate momentum y-component
	p_z	Candidate momentum z-component
	E	Candidate energy
Constituent features		
Category	Feature	Description
Kinematic	$\log p_T$	Log transverse momentum
	$\log E$	Log energy
	$\log(p_T^{\text{rel}})$	Log relative p_T w.r.t. jet
	$\log(E^{\text{rel}})$	Log relative energy
	$\Delta\eta$	Relative pseudorapidity from the jet axis
	$\Delta\phi$	Relative azimuthal angle from the jet axis
	ΔR	Angular distance to jet axis
Particle ID	isElectron	Electron indicator
	isMuon	Muon indicator
	isPhoton	Photon indicator
	isChargedHadron	Charged hadron indicator
	isNeutralHadron	Neutral hadron indicator
	charge	Candidate charge
Impact parameters	d_z	Longitudinal impact parameter
	$S_{d_z} = \frac{d_z}{\sigma(d_z)}$	Significance of the longitudinal impact parameter d_z
	d_{xy}	Transversal impact parameter
	$S_{d_{xy}} = \frac{d_{xy}}{\sigma(d_{xy})}$	Significance of the transversal impact parameter d_{xy}

3 Full reconstruction of τ_h

Hadronic tau reconstruction can be formulated as a set of supervised learning tasks that together define the properties of a τ_h candidate. In Refs. [24, 25], we established a unified framework addressing τ_h identification (isTau), decay mode classification (DM), and the regression of the visible transverse momentum of the generator-level τ_h (p_T^{vis}), achieving strong performance in all tasks. In the present study, we extend this framework to a more complete reconstruction of the τ_h by covering additional properties.

We now include charge reconstruction (q) as a binary classification problem and generalize the regression target to the full four-momentum (p^μ), predicting ($p_T^{\text{vis}}, \eta^{\text{vis}}, \phi^{\text{vis}}, m^{\text{vis}}$). The reconstruction is thus composed of four tasks:

$$\Phi(\text{jet features, particle features}) \rightarrow \{\text{isTau, DM, q, } p^\mu\},$$

where Φ is a trainable model.

We consider two complementary versions of Φ : SingleParTau, where each task is solved independently through per-task training, and MultiParTau, in which a single model is trained to solve all four tasks simultaneously. SingleParTau serves as a performance baseline, while MultiParTau allows the shared backbone to exploit correlations between the targets and provides a more parameter-efficient model for deployment. In all cases, the underlying model architecture is based on ParticleTransformer [23], which operates on the reconstructed particle flow candidates forming the jet. The overview of the model layouts is shown in Fig. 1.

The transformer backbone accounts for the bulk of the model size, with approximately 3.1 M parameters, and is nearly identical between SingleParTau and MultiParTau: the input embedding is shared and only the final output layer differs slightly depending on the task. An individual SingleParTau model is similar in size to the full MultiParTau model, at 3.48 M compared to 3.58 M parameters. The reduction in model complexity therefore does not arise from a smaller architecture, but from the fact that solving all four tasks with SingleParTau requires four independently trained models, amounting to a combined $4 \times 3.48 \text{ M} \approx 13.92 \text{ M}$ parameters. This is roughly four times that of MultiParTau, which instead reuses a single shared backbone across all four tasks with task-specific heads. This efficiency comes at a cost: optimizing four separate tasks through a shared network requires strict loss balancing to prevent the competing objectives from degrading overall performance.

3.1 Training strategy

Both the SingleParTau and MultiParTau models are trained for a maximum of 100 epochs using the AdamW optimizer [48] with a OneCycleLR scheduler utilizing a cosine annealing strategy. To ensure stable training and efficient convergence, we utilize 16-bit mixed-precision training. The training is done using NVIDIA L40s GPU with a batch size of 12 288. The input jets are zero-padded and capped at 20 constituents.

The ParticleTransformer [23] backbone architecture used by SingleParTau and MultiParTau consists of an input embedding layer, two transformer layers, and task-specific heads. The embedding network is a feedforward architecture composed of sequential linear, normalization, and activation layers, with hidden dimensions of [256, 512, 256] in both models. The transformer layers are standard ParticleTransformer layers, using the relative η and ϕ with respect to the jet axis of the constituents to define the particle attention matrix. No systematic hyperparameter or architecture optimization was done at this stage, but it is expected that a multi-objective tuning, taking into account the physics performance as well as computational performance, is straightforward and can further improve the physics reach.

Given that the prediction targets vary both in semantic meaning and data type, each training task must be treated individually with a task-specific objective and corresponding loss function. The following paragraphs detail the training targets and loss formulations employed for the four tasks and are summarized in Table 2.

τ_h identification (tagging): formulated as a binary classification task to distinguish jets originating from τ_h decays from background qq-jets. Each reconstructed jet is given a tag `isTau`, set to 1 if there is a matched τ_h^{gen} , and to 0 if there is no matched τ_h^{gen} . Similarly to Ref. [24], we use cross entropy loss (CEL) for the tagging task:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{tag}} = \mathcal{L}_{CEL}(w_i, \theta) \quad (2)$$

In Eq. 2 the parameter θ denotes the model parameters, and w_i the weight for the individual jet i based on its kinematics.

Kinematic reconstruction: a multi-target regression task aimed to reconstruct the full visible τ_h four-momentum. We chose the (p_T, η, φ, m) parametrization of the four-momentum to be reconstructed, but other parametrization are possible. We have chosen mass m as the fourth component as energy E is largely redundant given $m \ll p_T \cdot \cosh(\eta)$.

Each target contributes to the overall kinematics loss as:

$$\Lambda_p = \log \left(\frac{p_T^{\text{gen-}\tau}}{p_T^{\text{reco-jet}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\Lambda_\eta = \Delta^\pm \eta, \quad (4)$$

$$\Lambda_{s\varphi} = \sin(\Delta^\pm \varphi), \Lambda_{c\varphi} = \cos(\Delta^\pm \varphi) \quad (5)$$

$$\Lambda_m = \log \left(\frac{m^{\text{gen-}\tau}}{m^{\text{reco-jet}}} \right). \quad (6)$$

Here the Δ^\pm denotes the signed difference of the given property for the generator-level visible tau and the reconstruction-level jet. In case of φ we use the wrapped difference [49] as shown in Eq. 7:

$$\Delta^\pm \varphi = \text{atan2}(\sin(\Delta^\pm \varphi), \cos(\Delta^\pm \varphi)) \quad (7)$$

The first component of the overall kinematics loss is ‘‘chord’’ loss, which is the hypotenuse for a triangle with the sides corresponding to $\Lambda_{s\varphi}$ and $\Lambda_{c\varphi}$. All other components of the kinematics loss use Huber loss [50] with delta parameter set to 1.0 as shown in Eq. 8:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{kin}} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{chord}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{chord}}(\Lambda_{s\varphi}, \Lambda_{c\varphi}) + \sum_i \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_{\text{Huber}}(\Lambda_i)}{\lambda_{\text{chord}} + \sum_i \lambda_i} \quad (8)$$

with $i \in \{p, \eta, m\}$. As the τ_h visible mass is noisy due to the neutrinos in the τ_h decay escaping detection, we choose the weight for the mass component of the kinematics loss $\lambda_m = 0.2$ and set all other λ_i to 1, in order to down-weight the mass terms contribution to the kinematics loss.

Charge reconstruction: formulated as a binary classification problem, assigning each τ_h candidate to one of the two possible charges, $q^{\text{true}} = \pm 1$. For training purposes, the physical charge labels are mapped to binary class indices according to

$$y^{\text{charge}} = \begin{cases} 0, & q^{\text{true}} = -1 \\ 1, & q^{\text{true}} = +1 \end{cases}. \quad (9)$$

The network is designed with a two node output layer, where each node produces a logit corresponding to one of the two charge hypotheses. The model is trained using the cross-entropy loss function $\mathcal{L}_{\text{charge}} = \mathcal{L}_{CE}$. During inference, the predicted class index is mapped back to the corresponding physical charge assignment, $q^{\text{pred}} = \pm 1$.

Decay mode classification: a task assigning each τ_h candidate to one of six categories derived from the HPS [7, 10] decay mode indexing scheme, corresponding to the dominant τ_h decay modes defined by the multiplicity of charged hadrons (h^\pm) and neutral pions (π^0). The target class index $y_i^{\text{DM}} \in \{0, \dots, 5\}$ is defined as:

$$y_i^{\text{DM}} = \begin{cases} 0, & h^\pm \\ 1, & h^\pm \pi^0 \\ 2, & h^\pm + \geq 2\pi^0 \\ 3, & h^\pm h^\mp h^\pm \\ 4, & h^\pm h^\mp h^\pm + \geq \pi^0 \\ 5, & \text{rare modes} \end{cases} . \quad (10)$$

The target labels are one-hot encoded and the model is trained using the standard cross-entropy loss for multi-classification $\mathcal{L}_{\text{DM}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}$.

Table 2: Training types and loss functions for the four tasks needed for τ_h reconstruction

Task	Training type	Loss function
τ_h identification	binary classification	cross entropy (CE) loss
p^μ reconstruction	multi-target regression	Huber loss + ‘‘chord’’ loss
decay mode classification	multi-class classification	cross entropy (CE) loss
charge identification	binary classification	cross entropy (CE) loss

3.2 Unified model for full τ_h reconstruction

Training the multi-task model requires careful balancing of the loss across the task-specific heads. The difficulty arises from potential gradient interference, where updates for one task may negatively impact the performance of others. To address this, the multi-task MultiParTau model employs the PCGrad algorithm [51] that dynamically modifies the gradients of task-specific losses during training by reducing gradient interference between the four tasks during training. This helps the backbone model to learn features beneficial to all objectives aiming to reduce the negative weight updates on any one task in the process. As a safeguard, the gradients are clipped with a max norm of 1.0 after PCGrad merging and before the optimizer step to avoid destabilizing gradients.

As shown in Fig. 1, the MultiParTau model consists of a shared embedding layer and a common backbone that processes the constituents of the jet. Task separation is achieved using four dedicated CLS tokens that attend to the shared backbone output. Each task-specific token then passes through its own readout head to produce the final predictions. This architecture allows the model to learn a unified representation of the jet while maintaining specialized branches for each reconstruction task.

The total training loss for MultiParTau is a weighted combination of the four task-specific losses:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{multi}} = \sum_i \lambda_i w_i \mathcal{L}_i \quad \text{with } i \in \{\text{tag, kin, DM, charge}\} \quad (11)$$

where w_i denotes the kinematic-based sample weight.

Figure 1: Schematic of the model architectures of the two training approaches: **(Left)** Multi-task model features a common backbone shared among all four tasks **(Right)** Dedicated model has a separate backbone trained for each task. All task-specific heads consist of two linear layers, with the second layer having an output dimension of 128. Given the increased difficulty of the kinematic regression task, the kinematic head is the only one for which dropout is not applied.

3.3 Training convergence

The convergence behavior of the models is shown in Fig. 2. The training is stable and converges for both approaches across all four reconstruction tasks. MultiParTau reaches lower validation losses and shows smooth convergence throughout training, while SingleParTau exhibits a gradual increase in validation loss at later epochs for the classification tasks, indicating mild overfitting. For SingleParTau, the model checkpoint with the lowest validation loss is selected independently for each task and used for the performance evaluation. For MultiParTau, the final model checkpoint is selected according to the total validation loss summed across all four tasks. The vertical dashed line in Fig. 2 indicates the chosen checkpoint, which represents the best overall compromise between the four reconstruction objectives.

Figure 2: Evolution of the validation loss during training for the τ_h identification, decay mode classification, charge reconstruction, and kinematic regression tasks. Absolute validation loss values are shown for SingleParTau and MultiParTau, with the best validation epoch indicated. For MultiParTau, the model checkpoint selected for evaluation is also shown.

4 Results

The performance of the hadronic tau reconstruction models is characterized using dedicated, detailed metrics for each reconstruction task.

The **tau identification** performance is evaluated using the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, shown in Figure 3 (left), which displays the jet mis-identification rate P_{misid} as a function of the τ_h identification efficiency ϵ_τ . The signal efficiency is evaluated on $Z/\gamma^* \rightarrow \tau\tau$ jets matched to generator level τ_h , and the mis-identification rate on $Z/\gamma^* \rightarrow qq$ background jets, both required to satisfy $10^\circ < \theta < 170^\circ$ at generator and reconstruction level, with no minimum p_T requirement, in order to include low- p_T τ_h candidates relevant for the TeraZ physics program. The two approaches exhibit nearly identical performance over the full range of operating points, with MultiParTau performing slightly better. Figure 3 (right) shows the jet mis-identification rate per generator-level background-jet p_T bin at a fixed average τ_h identification efficiency of 80%. The mis-identification rate is significantly lower in the 0–5 GeV bin, where it is $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})$, rising to $\mathcal{O}(10^{-2})$ for jets above 5 GeV. This is because the score threshold is set for a global average efficiency of 80%, which corresponds to a signal efficiency of only $\sim 40\text{--}45\%$ in the 0–5 GeV bin, resulting in an effectively tighter selection on background jets in that region.

Figure 3: **(Left)** The jet mis-identification rate P_{misid} as a function of the τ_h identification efficiency ϵ_τ is nearly identical for SingleParTau and MultiParTau. **(Right)** The jet mis-identification rate per generator-level background jet p_T bin at a global average τ_h identification efficiency of 80%. The fake rate is $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})$ in the 0–5 GeV bin, rising to $\mathcal{O}(10^{-2})$ above 5 GeV, with both models performing comparably across the full p_T range.

For the **decay mode classification**, it is important to note that the different τ_h decay modes are not equally populated in the dataset. While the dominant channels are well represented, categories with multiple neutral pions as well as rare decays contain significantly fewer samples. To evaluate the classification performance across all decay modes, we use the class-wise F1 score, which combines the precision and recall of the classifier into a single metric to measure how accurately each decay mode is identified. Figure 4 (left) compares the F1 score of the SingleParTau and MultiParTau models for the individual generator-level τ_h decay modes, where the “Overall” category represents the average performance across all channels, weighted by the branching fractions of the corresponding τ_h decays.

Both approaches achieve very similar F1 scores of approximately 0.89–0.95 for the dominant channels. The best performance is obtained for the single charged hadron (h^\pm) decay mode, while the classification becomes more challenging for channels containing multiple neutral pions as well as for the statistically limited rare category. The MultiParTau model achieves slightly higher F1 scores across all decay modes, although the difference between the two approaches remains small. Figure 4 (right) shows the confusion matrix for the MultiParTau model, normalized to the generator-level true decay modes. The strong diagonal structure indicates that the classifier correctly identifies the true channel in the majority of events, with correctly reconstructed fractions reaching approximately 90–95% for the dominant channels. The largest off-diagonal contributions arise from migrations between categories with similar final state signatures, in particular between decay modes differing only in the number of reconstructed neutral pions. Mis-classifications involving the rare category are also observed more frequently due to the limited number of available events in these channels.

Figure 4: **(Left)** While both MultiParTau and SingleParTau have a similar performance, the unified model has consistently a slightly better performance measured in terms of F1 score, the harmonic mean of precision and recall. **(Right)** τ_h class-wise classification performance normalized over generator-level τ_h decay modes for MultiParTau.

In order to evaluate the performance on the **kinematic reconstruction** task, we use the median ΔR between the predicted and generator-level τ_h candidates for the angular component. For the momentum, we determine the resolution of the reconstructed visible transverse momentum p_T^{vis} as a function of the generator-level visible τ_h p_T . The p_T^{vis} resolution is quantified using the interquartile range (IQR) of the $p_T^{\text{pred}}/p_T^{\text{gen}}$ distribution, normalized to its median, providing a robust measure of the distribution width where smaller values correspond to a better momentum resolution while reducing sensitivity to outliers. In addition, two-dimensional distributions of the predicted and generator-level kinematic quantities are used to illustrate the agreement and resolution of the reconstructed p^μ components.

Figure 5 (left) shows the median ΔR between the predicted and generator-level τ_h candidates. The SingleParTau model achieves the best angular resolution over the full p_T range, with median ΔR values of approximately $3.1\text{--}3.7 \times 10^{-3}$. The MultiParTau model exhibits comparable angular performance, with median ΔR values of approximately $3.8\text{--}5.4 \times 10^{-3}$.

As a reconstruction-level cross-check, the same quantities are also computed using the original reconstructed jet features, denoted as RecoJet. This approach yields significantly larger median ΔR values of approximately $4.3\text{--}7.1 \times 10^{-3}$, indicating improved angular resolution for the ML-based approaches. All methods exhibit a gradual degradation in angular resolution with increasing τ_h transverse momentum. Figure 5 (right) shows the corresponding p_T^{vis} resolution. The SingleParTau model again provides the best overall performance, achieving an IQR-based momentum resolution of approximately 2.51–3.11% over the studied p_T range. The MultiParTau model exhibits nearly identical performance, achieving resolutions of approximately 2.54–3.20%, compared to 3.28–4.53% for the RecoJet approach. The momentum resolution improves with increasing p_T up to approximately 40 GeV, after which a slight deterioration is observed, reflecting the reduced number of available high- p_T jets in the dataset.

Figure 5: The dependence of the reconstructed τ_h median(ΔR) (**left**) and p_T^{vis} (**right**) of the generator-level visible τ_h p_T .

Figure 6 shows how well the four p^μ components are reconstructed for the SingleParTau model. Each panel shows a two-dimensional histogram of the predicted value against the generator-level truth, where a perfect reconstruction would place all jets exactly on the diagonal. For the two angular variables, the jet density sits tightly along the diagonal across the full range, consistent with the small median ΔR values seen in Fig. 5 (left). The visible transverse momentum is also well reconstructed, with the jet density following the diagonal closely. At higher p_T the spread grows, due to the limited number of high- p_T jets in the dataset. The visible invariant mass is noticeably harder to reconstruct, with the distributions spread more broadly and clustering near a few preferred values. This is because m^{vis} varies strongly with the τ_h decay mode, with each decay mode populating a different mass region, but the kinematic head receives no decay mode information and must infer the correct mass purely from the particle flow candidates of the reconstructed jet. Furthermore, since the τ_h decay produces a neutrino that escapes detection, m^{vis} does not take a single fixed value, which further complicates the regression.

Figure 6: True and predicted p^μ components for the SingleParTau.

The **charge reconstruction** performance is evaluated using the charge mis-identification rate, defined as the fraction of matched generator-level τ_h candidates for which the predicted charge differs from the true charge. As a reference, we compare the ML models to a conventional jet charge observable [52] denoted as QKappa:

$$Q^\kappa = \frac{1}{\left(p_T^{\text{jet}}\right)^\kappa} \sum_i q_i \left(p_T^i\right)^\kappa, \quad (12)$$

where the sum is taken over all particle flow candidates in the jet, with q_i and p_T^i denoting the charge and transverse momentum of the i -th candidate. The parameter κ controls the relative weighting of low- and high- p_T particle flow candidates. This observable provides a simple physics motivated estimate of the τ_h charge based on the momentum weighted distribution of the particle flow candidate charges.

Figure 7 (left) shows the charge mis-identification rate P_{misid} as a function of the charge identification efficiency ε_τ . The ML-based approaches exhibit very similar performance over the full efficiency range. Up to 80% efficiency, both SingleParTau and MultiParTau achieve charge mis-identification rates below 10^{-3} , with only small differences between them. The Qkappa baseline shows a mis-identification rate roughly one to two orders of magnitude larger than the ML-based approaches, demonstrating that the models exploit the particle flow candidate content of the reconstructed jet considerably more effectively than a fixed momentum weighted jet charge estimator. Figure 7 (right) shows P_{misid} as a function of the generator-level visible τ_h transverse momentum at fixed charge identification efficiencies of 99%, 95%, and 70%. At all three working points, both ML-based models achieve a stable mis-identification rate across the full p_T range, with no significant degradation at low transverse momentum. The Qkappa baseline exhibits a substantially higher and more p_T -dependent mis-identification rate, particularly at high- p_T where the momentum weighting of the jet charge estimator loses discriminating power. Both SingleParTau and MultiParTau perform comparably across all working points and p_T values, with MultiParTau maintaining a slight advantage consistent with the behaviour observed in the other classification tasks.

Figure 7: Charge reconstruction performance for SingleParTau, MultiParTau, and the QKappa baseline. **(Left)** Charge mis-identification rate P_{misid} as a function of the charge identification efficiency ε_τ . **(Right)** P_{misid} as a function of the generator-level visible τ_h transverse momentum at fixed charge identification efficiencies of 99%, 95%, and 70%. Both models show very similar performance and significantly outperform the Q_κ baseline.

5 Summary and Outlook

In this paper, we extend the unified ParticleTransformer-based τ_h reconstruction approach established in Ref. [25] to a more complete set of reconstruction tasks. In addition to τ_h identification and decay mode classification, we incorporate charge identification (q) and full visible four-momentum regression ($p^\mu = (p_T^{\text{vis}}, \eta^{\text{vis}}, \phi^{\text{vis}}, m^{\text{vis}})$), bringing the total to four addressed tasks. We also introduce two complementary training strategies: SingleParTau, where a dedicated model is trained independently for each task, and MultiParTau, where a single model is trained to solve all four tasks simultaneously. Both are evaluated

on the newly introduced version of the Future dataset, based on a full simulation of the CLD detector concept for the FCC-ee TeraZ run.

The MultiParTau approach slightly outperforms SingleParTau on the three classification tasks (τ_h identification, decay mode classification, and charge reconstruction) while using approximately one-quarter of the trainable parameters. The relatively small performance differences between the two approaches indicate that both models achieve excellent classification performance, while suggesting that the shared backbone is able to learn representations that are effective across multiple tasks. The only task for which SingleParTau has an advantage in is kinematic reconstruction, where it achieves the smallest median ΔR and the best p_T^{vis} resolution. Nevertheless, the performance gap in kinematic reconstruction remains modest, demonstrating that a unified multi-task architecture can successfully address the full τ_h reconstruction problem.

For τ_h identification, both approaches achieve jet mis-identification rates of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-3})$ at a global average identification efficiency of 80%. Decay mode classification yields F1 scores of approximately 0.89–0.95 for the dominant decay channels, while charge reconstruction achieves mis-identification rates below 10^{-3} up to an efficiency of 80%, outperforming the QKappa baseline by one to two orders of magnitude. For kinematic reconstruction, SingleParTau achieves median ΔR values of $3.1\text{--}3.7 \times 10^{-3}$ and p_T^{vis} resolutions of 2.51–3.11%, while MultiParTau achieves comparable performance with median ΔR values of $3.8\text{--}5.4 \times 10^{-3}$ and p_T^{vis} resolutions of 2.54–3.20%. The original reconstructed jet four-momentum is included as a reconstruction-level cross-check, yielding worse performance than the ML-based models for the considered kinematic observables.

This work presents the first realistic high-performance ML-based hadronic τ reconstruction approach for FCC-ee studies, offering τ_h identification, charge reconstruction, decay mode classification, and full visible four-momentum reconstruction. The resulting models provide high-level reconstructed τ_h objects suitable for future FCC-ee analyses, while the MultiParTau approach demonstrates that strong performance across all reconstruction tasks can be achieved with a single unified model.

Future work will focus on further improving τ_h reconstruction by extending the set of targeted decay modes, including a dedicated class for kaon enriched rare decays, and by incorporating additional information such as secondary vertices. It will also be interesting to study how performance scales with the size of the training dataset through dedicated ablation studies. Finally, extending the scope to include neutrino reconstruction would represent an important step towards a more complete description of τ_h decays.

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Data availability

The dataset used in this paper is made available in Ref. [32]. The software used to produce the results can be found in Ref. [53].

Author contributions (CRediT)

Nalong-Norman Seeba: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **Laurits**

Tani: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding administration. **Torben Lange:** Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding administration. **Joosep Pata:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding administration.

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